

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D5.3

Final version of advanced autonomous
functionalities for aerial robots

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMCL	Adaptive Monte Carlo Localization
DLL	Direct LIDAR Localization
DMS	Data Management System
EKF	Extended Kalman Filter
ENU	East-North-Up
FSM	Finite State Machine
GCS	Ground Control Station
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
gRCS	General Robot Control Station
GPS	Global Positioning System
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IVP	Intelligence and Visualization Portal
I&M	Inspection and Maintenance
KF	Kalman Filter
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
RANSAC	Random Sample Consensus
RCS	Robot Control Station
RGB	Red, Green, Blue
RMCP	Robotic Mobile Contact Platform
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
UGV	Unmanned ground vehicle
UWB	Ultra-Wideband
VO	Visual Odometry
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of the document

This document aims to introduce the final version of algorithms developed for aerial inspection robots that deal with GNSS-free navigation and aerial contact control. This deliverable is a result of the work carried out in tasks T5.1 and T5.3.

PILOTING use-cases involve multiple challenges for inspection and maintenance operations using aerial robots, including physical interaction with the environment, drone aerodynamic interactions with nearby surfaces, lack of GNSS signals, unstructured environments, irregular lighting conditions, among others. To overcome these challenges, the proposed I&M Platform features autonomous functionalities that enable aerial robots safely and autonomously complete contact and non-contact inspection missions. The autonomous functionalities for aerial robots are classified into two sets of categories: autonomous control while contacting the surface including autonomous take-off and landing, and autonomous safe navigation in GNSS-denied environments.

The autonomous control while contacting the surface is essential as it allows aerial robots to perform advanced physical-contact inspections. These functionalities were developed in task T5.3. The autonomous navigation functionalities enable aerial robots to navigate environments safely and reach desired inspection locations in complex, highly cluttered, unstructured environments. These functionalities were developed in T5.1.

1.2 Structure of the document

The structure of this document consists of three main sections. In Section 2, the general hypotheses and design of the localization and navigation methods of all PILOTING aerial robots is presented, along with specific implementations for each of them as well as validations obtained in experiments conducted in the PILOTING use-cases. This section summarizes the functionalities developed in task T5.1. In Section 3, which focuses on task T5.3, the generic dynamic model and modular controller scheme to adapt to every aerial robot interaction control are introduced. Finally, Section 4 closes the document with the conclusions and accomplishments performed with the methods developed.

2. GNSS-free localization and navigation for aerial systems

2.1 Introduction

As presented in deliverable D5.1, the general architecture for GNSS-free navigation for the PILOTING aerial robots relies on three main modules: planning, perception, and control. The architecture is modular and does not constrain the type of algorithms for any of the modules and enables parallel development of methods and algorithms. The planning module receives the mission from the robot control station (also known as GCS). It includes the algorithms for trajectory planning and replanning in case of obstacle detection. The planning module adopted in PILOTING for GNSS-free navigation was presented in deliverable D4.1. For brevity, the description of the planning module is not included in this deliverable.

The perception module is responsible for estimating the robot pose (position and attitude) and increasing the situational awareness of the aerial robot, including functionalities such as estimating the height to the landing site, estimating the distance to the surface in which the aerial robot will make contact, or obstacle detection. The control module receives the tracking commands from the planning module, and uses the estimates obtained by the perception module (robot pose, distance to the contact surface, among others) to determine the command actions that are given to the aerial robot low-level controllers. The advanced functionalities related to this block are described in Section 3 of this document.

The performance and uncertainty levels of the perception system are critical for the GNSS-free navigation of the aerial robot. Each different PILOTING aerial robot and use case requires a specific perception system, depending on its particularities and available sensors on board each aerial robot. The architecture and fundamentals of the developed perception module were presented in D5.1. This section describes the new developments performed in T5.1 for the GNSS-free localization of each aerial robot and shortly evaluates their performance in experiments performed in the PILOTING scenarios.

2.2 General aspects of PILOTING aerial robot localization

The objective is to estimate the 6 DoF (Degree or Freedom) pose, i.e. 3D localization and 3D attitude, of the robots in GNSS-denied scenarios. GNSS-denied localization is one of the key functionalities to enable autonomous navigation and inspection with aerial robots in PILOTING scenarios. Each type of PILOTING type of inspection has its own specific characteristics, and hypotheses. That is why each PILOTING robot requires different types of localization methods. However, it is possible to extract a set of common aspects that will be adopted for every of the GNSS-free aerial robot pose estimation methods that have been developed.

To enhance modularity and ease of use, all developed GNSS-free localization methods use only **on-board sensors and on-board processing** in such a way that the robots require no infrastructure in

the scenario. Although deliverable D5.1 considered the possibility of using a Total Station for the GNSS-free localization of VIAD-DRONE aerial robot, this idea has not been implemented. Instead, an efficient multi-sensor perception approach using onboard sensors has been adopted for VIAD-DRONE.

In some cases, the perception method will make use of a **3D map of the scenario** or of the structure to be inspected. This map could be an already existing digital twin (i.e., an accurate model of the infrastructure to inspect) or generated for the inspection tasks. The format of this map will be a 3D point cloud. As presented in D5.1, in the envisioned use cases, the 3D map will be obtained with a Total Station system (viaduct and refinery use cases) or with a 3D LiDAR (tunnel scenarios where the map is built with a 3D LiDAR mounted on the CART robotic vehicle).

The 3D map of the scenario is the base of the autonomous inspection. It defines a global fixed reference frame linked to the infrastructure, where the position of the defects or the desired points for inspection are referred to. This reference frame is time-consistent and allows to re-visit the same positions over and over at different times, even at different years as we demonstrated in PILOTING experiments. This reference is expressed in ENU (East-North-Up) to be aligned with global coordinate systems such as GNSS. The map enables obtaining a **global localization** with respect to the infrastructure. Global localization must be accurate to enable precise localization of defects, inspection of the desired areas of the infrastructure, or re-visit the same positions for defect analysis and evaluation.

The perception methods for other PILOTING aerial robots make use of **localization with respect to a common pose in that mission** (called **relative localization** in deliverable D4.1), for instance the take-off pose. The accuracy of this type of localization is similar to that of global localization, however, it requires determining the transformation between the reference frame used for this localization and the global reference frame. In these aerial robots, both localization systems are integrated. These aerial robots maintain a relative localization for the aerial robot control while an independent global localization finds the relation (or transform) between the local and the global reference systems, so the inspection points can be translated.

Hence, all PILOTING aerial robots, independently whether they use global localization or localization w.r.t. a common point, operate as specified in deliverable D3.1. The points to be inspected are selected in the Intelligence and Visualization Portal (IVP) and sent, through the Data Management System (DMS), to the General Robot Control Station (gRCS), where the trajectory plan is decided. The points to be inspected and the aerial robot trajectory waypoints are all expressed in global coordinates to facilitate re-visit and defect evolution monitoring and enable inspection of the same points by different robots possibly using different types of localization.

The next subsections describe the GNSS-free localization methods developed for each PILOTING aerial robot and inspection use cases.

2.3 Viaduct visual inspection

2.3.1 Introduction

This use case is performed by the AERO-CAM robotic platform, which has a high-resolution camera on top of a gimbal to take pictures. For the localization, the platform uses a combination of sensors including LIDAR, IMU or altimeter, all centralized in an Intel Nuc i7 onboard computer. This robotic platform has not changed at the hardware level since the last deliverable.

2.3.2 Hypotheses

The localization approach for the visual inspection of the viaduct has not changed since the last deliverable 5.1. This approach requires the creation of a previous 3D map with a total station. This map is represented as a point cloud whose origin establishes the coordinate system of the entire inspection system. In addition, this map will be reused in future inspections since the infrastructure does not suffer significant changes in its useful life. These inspections will be commanded as specific points or areas of the viaduct to be photographed, which may be pillars or decks.

Like all the aerial platforms in this section, AERO-CAM requires establishing a global positioning with respect to the map. In this platform it is especially important, since it has a positioning system relative to the starting point of the platform, so it is necessary to relate this positioning to the global map. Therefore, there are two algorithms, one for global localization and the other for relative localization.

Figure 1. AERO-CAM full transformation system.

This whole concept can be illustrated in Figure 1. The system is seen as a transform tree, where T_{GL} represents the transform between the map and the take-off point. T_{LD} represents the relative navigation of the UAV from the take-off point. However, both transforms can suffer drifts or offsets, so the transform T_{GD} is established, which serves to update the position of the UAV relative to the map while flying.

2.3.3 GNSS-free 6 DoF pose estimation

The two localization algorithms are explained below:

Global localization system

The global localization algorithm is based on DLL [1], a direct LIDAR localization algorithm. This method receives as input a previous map of the environment, an estimated initial pose and the LIDAR point cloud along with an estimate of the UAV odometry and IMU.

The pre-map needs to be processed the first time it is used, as this is a costly procedure. This processing consists of constructing a 3D grid of the map size, where for each vertex of that grid the minimum distance to a point in the point cloud is calculated. Thus, when the algorithm receives the point cloud from the LIDAR, a trilinear interpolation with the pre-computed map is performed for each point. This calculation is performed because for each point introduced in the grid, there are 8 vertices adjacent to the subcube to which it belongs. The global localization algorithm considers these distances to repeat the operation by optimizing them through a nonlinear optimizer until a local minimum is reached.

Due to the nature of the nonlinear optimizer, the risk of the result being an invalid local minimum is very high, so the initial guess that serves as input to the algorithm is very important. Although this guess does not require absolute precision, it is recommended that it be approximate for better convergence. To quantify the quality required for this initial guess, an experimental study has been carried out by testing different guesses on real viaduct data. Specifically, for the data used, a ground truth obtained with a total station is already available, so that the results can be validated.

Figure 2. Experimental results on the variation of the initial guess of the DLL algorithm for a viaduct.

Figure 2 shows the experimental results of varying the initial guess in the different position axes (x, y, z) and yaw. It can be observed the range of values for which the algorithm manages to correctly solve the localization (green dots), while there is a further range for which the algorithm starts to fail (red dots). The ground truth position is marked in blue. These values represent offsets, not absolute positioning values.

At the implementation level, the algorithm has been programmed in C++ using the ROS framework. The Ceres library is used to solve the nonlinear optimization process. At the interface level, the algorithm receives the information from the IMU of the AERO-CAM, as well as the odometry through ROS topics. For the alignment request, a service has been prepared that can be called at any time to request asynchronous processing. The input parameters are the initial guess and the point cloud of the lidar to be aligned with the map. As a result, a pose with the solution is returned.

As explained in the previous deliverable, the global positioning system has a crucial mission, since establishing the relationship between the UAV and the map allows the correct performance of inspections without having to maintain the same exact take-off position between flights or the need for a total station. The algorithm allows to operate always with the same coordinate system, even with inspections performed on different days or times of the year.

This algorithm is not executed on the on-board computer but on the ground computer. In this way, the computational load is relieved since this algorithm does not need to be executed in real time. The procedure is carried out just before take-off, to localize AERO-CAM with respect to the viaduct. Also, the process is executed asynchronously with a variable periodicity during the flight, thus updating the T_{GD} transform.

Relative localization system

On the other hand, the relative localization algorithm is in charge of obtaining the odometry between the take-off point and the UAV with a high frequency. This localization is used by the aircraft control to fly safely and complete the mission. Following the scheme of Figure 1, this localization oversees finding the T_{LD} transform. The origin of this localization is not important since it will be the global localization algorithm of the previous section that will relate this odometry to the previous map. Therefore, this localization, although in a normal operation has its origin at the take-off point, it can be initiated at any point of the flight. This can be especially useful if a manual takeoff is performed or if, for some reason, the relative localization requires a restart.

This relative localization is performed entirely in the on-board computer with on-board sensors. Specifically, use is made of LIDAR and a 9-axis IMU to calculate the UAV's pose. As mentioned above, the algorithm operates at a high frequency so that the control can use it. The algorithm is designed to send updates at the IMU frequency.

As explained in the previous deliverable, the relative localization algorithm is based on LIO-SAM [2]. Briefly, this algorithm establishes a tightly coupled fusion between LIDAR and IMU, builds a factor graph in which the sensor measurements are integrated to build and optimize a map from scratch.

Since the last deliverable, several enhancements have been introduced that have improved the performance of the algorithm. On the one hand, it was detected that the problem of asynchronous reception of IMU messages plays a crucial role in the performance of the algorithm. This is because the algorithm pre-integrates linear accelerations and angular velocities in a discrete way, so that inaccuracies in the time stamps of these messages distort the results of the operation.

Another problem identified is that the algorithm takes gravity as a numerical constant. Of course, there may be deviations in the IMU measurements or the gravity constant itself may be inaccurate by decimal digits, which may result in errors in localization. Therefore, a self-calibration process has been introduced whereby the UAV, before takeoff, takes a static gravity reading to store this empirical data.

As a result of the first pilots, other errors could also be identified and corrected. For example, when the system starts there was an error that could not align the initial position of the AERO-CAM with the origin of the map that creates the relative location. This had a huge influence since this offset invalidated all the efforts of the global localization algorithm to solve the problem, there was always a small error impossible to correct. Therefore, a thorough revision of the procedure has been carried out to eliminate this initial offset.

Again, the implementation of this relative location algorithm has been done in C++ using the ROS framework. The GTSAM library has been used for the implementation of the factor graphs. At the interface level, the algorithm receives information from the IMU and the LIDAR through topics. To establish the position and orientation of the sensors on the UAV, the ROS transform package is being used, which statically publishes this data.

2.3.4 Validation

The validation of the global and relative location algorithms of the AERO-CAM platform has been carried out on a real viaduct such as the "Arroyo del Espinazo" viaduct in Alora, Spain. These experiments have been treated as real inspections of the infrastructure, targeting specific areas and points of the viaduct. All the experiments have been commanded with the gRCS developed for all PILOTING robotic platforms. The validation has been done using the total station to obtain a ground truth measurement with which to compare the results.

The localization algorithms of this platform have undergone a significant evolution since the previous deliverable. While it is true that the approach has not changed and the structure remains the same, it has been possible to work on improving the accuracy and overall performance of the algorithms.

Figure 3 shows the comparative of this localization evolution, where the same is validated in the same experiment on the real viaduct. On the one hand, the ground-truth obtained with the total station is shown in green. The steps observed in these data correspond to the loss of the direct line of sight between the total station and the on-board prism due to a visual obstacle such as a tree or the viaduct itself. The orange line corresponds to the result of the algorithm after the implementation of the previous deliverable D5.1, while the blue line shows the new implementation presented in this document. An improvement in both accuracy and smoothness can be observed, since all the odometry has been smoothed, avoiding noisy signals such as those shown in the X axis in the figure.

Figure 3. Results of the AERO-CAM localization in the execution of an inspection mission on the viaduct. The green line is the ground-truth, yellow is the previous localization algorithm, while blue line shows the result of the current algorithm.

In short, this new implementation validates the proposed location solution for the inspection of viaducts. It has been possible to obtain a flexible and accurate solution with which to perform general and specific inspections in the PILOTING project.

2.4 Refinery pipes inspection

2.4.1 Introduction

The refinery pipeline inspection use case requires the HYBRID flight platform, which can fly to detect the pipeline and hover over it to allow the satellite robot to operate and perform the contact inspection.

The aerial platform has several on-board sensors for navigation. On the one hand, it has two LIDARs, one 3D and the other 2D. It also has a depth camera that provides RGB image information in addition to a point cloud. It also has a 9-axis IMU to complete the navigation information. This configuration is an important change from the previous deliverable for a correct evolution of the aerial platform. In this last iteration, the need for the mirror for the 3D LIDAR proposed in the previous deliverable has been eliminated, since the introduction of the 2D LIDAR fulfills the same function, reducing the overall weight of the system and the computation required by the embedded computer. The final

choice of sensors has been made after an intense phase of experimentation with the algorithms described below.

2.4.2 Hypotheses

The localization procedure for the HYBRID platform has many similarities with the one previously presented for the AERO-CAM. Here the concept of global and relative localization is repeated. On the one hand, a previous 3D map of the refinery obtained through a total station is available. This 3D map is again represented as a point cloud and will be used for all inspections to be performed at that location. The goal of the aerial platform is to land on a specific point of a pipeline, which is the input it receives in the inspection plan. This inspection point is reached thanks to the relative navigation algorithm, which calculates the movement of the UAV with the on-board sensors. The HYBRID makes use of two relative algorithms, one that calculates its movement using LIDAR and IMU, just like AERO-CAM, and the other that detects and locates the target pipeline, to accurately calculate the landing point.

Figure 4. HYBRID full transformation system.

Figure 4 illustrates the transform system of the whole process. The T_{GL} transform that relates the previous 3D map to the relative location from the take-off point can be seen. Like AERO-CAM, this relation can be recalculated during the flight to avoid drift. The transform T_{LD} is the pose calculated by the relative location. Finally, the transform T_{DP} is computed with the pipeline detection algorithm and returns the pose to the landing point.

2.4.3 GNSS-free 6 DoF pose estimation

The two localization algorithms are explained below:

Global localization system

The global localization algorithm is based on AMCL, Adaptive Monte Carlo Localization [3]. AMCL is a probabilistic algorithm that uses a particle filter to estimate the position and orientation of an aerial vehicle within a previously known 3D map, based on the onboard sensor readings. This provides the T_{GL} transform, which relates the relative position to the global position. In addition, as

its name suggests, the algorithm can adjust the number of particles during execution to reduce the computational load, which is essential since the algorithm is going to be running onboard. Our implementation uses a LiDAR sensor and an IMU.

Basically, every particle set consists of N particles, each one containing the following state vector, \mathbf{p}_i :

$$\mathbf{p}_i = [x \ y \ z \ \psi]$$

Which represents the position ($x \ y \ z$) and yaw angle (ψ) of the UAV at a certain point. Note how the robot roll and pitch angles are not included into the robot pose definition. We assume that these angles are available and accurate enough in an aerial vehicle using its onboard IMU. Every particle has, additionally, an associated weight (w_i), which indicates how likely that particle is to correctly represent the UAV state at that filter update.

Below, the stages in which the algorithm consists of will be presented in a simplified way. This will include an initialization phase and three stages, as shown in Figure 5.

- **Initialization phase:** At the very beginning, a set of particles is randomly distributed following a Gaussian distribution around an initial guessed position, with a similar weight for each one. Of course, the better this guess is, the faster the filter converges into a solution.
- **Prediction phase:** Using the odometry, we can calculate the displacement of the UAV from the last filter update. This information is used to compute the prior distribution of the particle cloud. That is, every particle is displaced using this information to get a new distribution.
- **Update phase:** The acquired point cloud is transformed to each particle pose to find correspondences between such cloud and what the map should look like from that particle's pose. Since this is very expensive computationally, we first compute a 3-D probability grid as in the study by Hornung et al., [4]. In this work, each position stores a value of how likely it is that such position falls within an occupied point of the map, instead of storing binary information about occupancy as in the provided map. Each 3D position \mathbf{p}_i of the grid is then filled with probability values according to a specific Gaussian distribution centered in the closest occupied point in the map and whose variance σ^2 depends on the sensor noise used in the approach. Then, for every point of the sensor point cloud, we access its corresponding value in the 3D probability grid. Such value would be an indicator of how likely a point is to be part of the map. By doing this with every point of the cloud and adding all the probability values, we obtain an estimation of how well that particle fits the true location of the aerial robot according to the map.
- **Resampling phase:** This is where the "Adaptive" part of the algorithm takes part. The main idea of this method is to bound the error introduced by the sample-based representation of the particulate filter. For this purpose, it is assumed that the actual a posteriori distribution is given by a precise and constant distribution. For this representation, it's possible to find the number of samples or particles that fulfill the distance between the estimated maximum likelihood and the actual probability does not exceed a certain threshold value.

Figure 5. AMCL algorithm architecture.

At the implementation level, the algorithm has been programmed in C++ using the ROS framework. At the interface level, the algorithm receives the information from the IMU of the HYBRID, as well as the odometry and LiDAR point cloud through ROS topics. The input is the initial guess values $(x \ y \ z \ \psi)$ for the UAV position. A ROS service has been implemented for further iterations of this initial guess if needed, to improve the filter performance.

Relative localization system

As mentioned in the introduction, the relative localization has two parts. On the one hand a localization from the take-off point (T_{LD}) which is mainly used by the control for the safe navigation of the platform since a high frequency odometry is provided. This algorithm is the same as the one used by the AERO-CAM platform for the viaduct visual inspection use case explained in section 2.3.3. Therefore, to avoid duplication, the method will not be explained again here.

On the other hand, the algorithm for pipeline detection will be presented below. The objective of this algorithm is to perform the detection relative to the UAV pose of the pipelines and, with this, to obtain the desired transformation to the landing point, T_{DP} .

After the intense phase of experimentation, it was concluded that it was necessary to have a robust estimation of the pipe even when landed on it, when the distance between the pipe and the sensor is close. For this reason, the use of 2D LiDAR has been chosen since it gives us a robust observation of the pipe.

Figure 6. Relative localization with pipe diagram.

Figure 6 shows a diagram of the pipeline detection algorithm architecture. In the following, each module will be discussed:

- **Cloud Pipe Detector:** This algorithm is based on the one proposed in [5]. The algorithm takes as input the point cloud of the depth camera and has two stages: point cloud pre-processing and target pipe pose estimation. In a simplified way, a Euclidean clustering of the point cloud will be performed and then a RANSAC (Random Sample Consensus) will be applied to each cluster to calculate the cylinder model that best fits the distribution of the cluster points. With this model, the model of the cylinder observed by the camera will be estimated.
- **Laser Pipe Detector:** This algorithm uses the measurements of the 2D LiDAR, which is placed perpendicular to the pipes to be detected. As in the case of the point cloud, the algorithm consists of two stages: a first preprocessing stage and a second stage of pipeline estimation. In the first phase, a Euclidean clustering will also be performed to obtain the subsets of points that could be a section of the pipeline. Once these sets of points of pipe sections are obtained, a circle fitting will be performed using a least squares method for each point, $P_i(x_i, y_i)$, of each cluster:

$$\begin{bmatrix} A \\ B \\ C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_i x_i^2 & \sum_i x_i y_i & \sum_i x_i \\ \sum_i x_i y_i & \sum_i y_i^2 & \sum_i y_i \\ \sum_i x_i & \sum_i y_i & \sum_i 1 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} -\sum_i (x_i^3 + x_i y_i^2) \\ -\sum_i (x_i^2 y_i + y_i^3) \\ -\sum_i (x_i^2 + y_i^2) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$A = -2a; B = -2b; C = a^2 + b^2 - r^2 \quad (5)$$

Where (a, b) and r are the center position and the radius of the estimated circle, respectively.

- **Pipes Global Database:** The objective of this module is to track the global frame of each estimated pipeline and to perform a fusion of the observations made by each sensor. In this way, it will be possible to work with different types of data such as the estimation of the cylinder made by RANSAC and the estimation of the pipe section made by means of the least squares method. In general, the operation of this module is as follows: Each time a new

observation arrives, regardless of which sensor, it will be evaluated whether it is associated to a pipe already existing in the database or it will be necessary to create a new instance. In the case where a new instance should be created, a Kalman Filter will be created with a static motion model to filter and merge the measurements made. In the case where the observation corresponds to a pipe already existing in the database, a fusion between the observation and the Kalman Filter estimate will be performed to calculate the new pipe dimension and the filter will be updated. This will allow the estimation of the pipe dimensions, such as its radius and length, to calculate its position in the global frame.

2.4.4 Validation

The proposed localization method for the HYBRID platform has been preliminarily functionally validated. This has been done using a hardware configuration with the final sensors installed, so that a person at hand can simulate the flight of the platform over a pipeline.

Figure 7. HYBRID pipe detection algorithm experiment.

Figure 7 shows a validation experiment in the CATEC indoor mockup. The RGB axis above is the center of mass of the sensors. The image shows the 3D lidar point cloud (white dots). The horizontal green line on the ground is the 2D lidar reading. The green cylinder is the estimate of the pipe detection algorithm at a given instant, while the purple cylinder is the global cylinder recorded over time when all detections are merged.

It is important to note that, since the flight platform is in the validation phase at the time of writing, it has not yet been possible to perform an in-flight validation of the algorithms. Once everything is

integrated and validated, real experiments will be performed and the results will be shown in deliverable D8.2.

2.5 Refinery tank inspection

2.5.1 Introduction

The use case of the refinery tank inspection requires the AEROX flight platform, which can perform contact inspections thanks to the robotic arm installed on it. The AEROX platform is also equipped with a 9-axis IMU and a barometric altimeter, as well as an integrated GPS receiver for global positioning (although the latter is managed with prudence for reasons explained below).

2.5.2 Hypotheses

To fully complete the inspection, AEROX must first navigate from its take-off point to the contact zone in the tank where the inspection is performed. Once there, the end effector will contact the tank and the platform will run its control algorithm while getting feedback from the robotic arm sensors. Therefore, the contact inspection system has two phases, an approach phase and a contact phase. As a necessary input to the system, the coordinates of the point in the tank where the inspection is to begin must be available. A 3D map of the tank is also available to relate the measurements to it. This 3D map has been created by a total station (Leica), which is also available during the inspection by tracking the AEROX platform through an on-board optical prism.

2.5.3 GNSS-free 6 DoF pose estimation

A flight mission of the AEROX system can be divided into two phases:

Approach

The approach phase from the take-off point to the contact with the tank is entirely dependent on the pilot. During this phase, the pilot must carefully guide the system onto the tank's surface, exerting sufficient pressure to establish contact. Once contact is made, the pilot can switch to autonomous control. At any time, the pilot retains authority to retrieve the platform from its contact mode if flight conditions deteriorate for any reason.

In terms of aircraft location, the GPS receiver is used during this approach phase since the pilot is in control. The location of the total station, which relates the 3D map to the movement, is also available.

Contact inspection

During the contact phase, the GPS signal may be degraded due to high interference from metallic structures in the environment. As a result, the AEROX platform relies on a combination of on-board sensors located along both the manipulator arm and the RMCP (Robotic Mobile Contact Platform) to compute its relative location. This is done by computing the inverse kinematics of the manipulator

through all degrees of freedom of the manipulator. This can be seen in Figure 8, where a Denavit-Hartenberg schematic of the AEROX platform is shown. However, this method only provides a pose relative to the RMCP's position. To achieve global localization, an additional step must be taken.

Figure 8. Denavit-Hartenberg scheme of the AEROX platform.

The step from relative to global localization is provided by total station position estimator that receives the laser-tracked coordinates from an on-board prism. It then assumes that the RMCP is in contact with the tank's surface and performs a numerical computation to determine the only possible position that would comply with the geometric constraints between the AEROX and the tank. Figure 9 illustrates the complete scheme of global and relative localization together at the moment of contact with the surface of a tank, represented as a yellow arc.

Figure 9. Leica-based position estimator algorithm visualization.

2.5.4 Validation

The validation of the AEROX platform has been particular since it uses the total station itself for the execution of the inspection, the results cannot be compared with the ground-truth. Therefore, the fact of completing the inspection correctly validates the localization algorithm itself, since the total station guarantees millimetre accuracy. Then, the validation results will be incorporated in deliverable D8.2.

2.6 Viaduct bearings inspection, and sensor and target installation

2.6.1 Introduction

The GNSS-free 6 DoF pose estimation methods for the viaduct are strongly dependent on the type of inspections and missions defined for this scenario. First, the missions are summarized in Section 2.6.2. Section 2.6.3 presents the main hypotheses used for the development of the localization method. The exteroceptive sensors mounted on board VIAD-DRONE, which are the basis for the GNSS-free 6 DoF pose estimation methods, are presented in Section 2.6.4. The GNSS- 6-DoF pose

estimation methods are presented in Section 2.6.5, and briefly validated in experiments in the PILOTING scenarios in Section 2.6.6.

2.6.2 Viaduct inspection missions

The viaduct use case considers three different missions that must be performed autonomously by the VIAD-DRONE aerial robot: *bearings inspection*, *sensor installation*, and *target installation*. PILOTING includes two different types of contact inspection for viaducts: deck contact and pillar contact. Accurate aerial pose estimation is critical to enable re-visiting the same inspection points for defect evolution monitoring. More details about VIAD-DRONE, its design and hardware components can be found in deliverable D4.3.

For the *bearings inspection* task, a camera is mounted on board VIAD-DRONE to capture images to inspect the bearings of the viaduct. The camera is gimbal-stabilized to improve the quality of the images. For the *sensor installation*, a sensor box is placed autonomously inside the hole at the top of the viaduct pillar to gather different structural measurements, such as vibration. Both tasks need the aerial robot to: i) establish physical contact on the viaduct deck and ii) move on the viaduct deck using the robot caterpillars until the robot is located at the top of the pillar. Hence, the start of both types of missions are similar. Next, the robot inserts the box inside the hole (*sensor installation* mission) or acquires images from vantage points to better perform bearing inspection (*bearings inspection* mission).

In *target installation* missions the aerial robot deploys, through physical contact, targets at specific points on the pillar surface. These targets are used to mark the location of cracks or defects in the infrastructure selected for inspection by the operator. The planning for this type of missions is as follows: 1) *Start*, the VIAD-DRONE takes-off from a known position, 2) *Approach*, where the aerial robot navigates towards the inspection area, and 3) *Attachment*, where the UAV performs contact with the pillar to deploy the markers at the specified locations in global coordinates.

Figure 10 summarizes the three types of missions. The pictures shown and experiment shown was performed in viaduct “Arroyo del Espinazo” in Álona, Spain.

Figure 10. Scheme with the general planning of missions for viaduct inspection: a) *sensor installation mission*. b) *bearings inspection mission*, and c) *target installation mission*. The pictures shown and experiment shown was performed in viaduct “Arroyo del Espinazo” in Álona, Spain.

2.6.3 Hypotheses of the VIAD-DRONE GNSS-free 6-DoF pose estimation

The GNSS-free 6-DoF pose estimation method developed for the VIAD-DRONE aerial robot is based on the following reasonable hypotheses:

- The viaduct deck must be within the VIAD-DRONE 2D LiDAR range along the full mission. The VIAD-DRONE perception system requires obtaining 2D LiDAR measurements of the viaduct deck. This hypothesis imposes using a 2D LiDAR with a sufficient range to cover the ground-deck distances.

- As a consequence of the previous hypothesis, the VIAD-DRONE position during the full mission, including the take-off and landing location, must be located below the viaduct deck. The VIAD-DRONE 3D LiDAR is modified using a mirror, see Section 2.6.4, to measure the vertical distance between the aerial robot and the deck.
- The viaduct pillar must be always within the field-of-view of the 2D LiDAR. The VIAD-DRONE perception system requires obtaining 2D LiDAR measurements from the pillar. This assumption is naturally imposed by the inspection missions in the viaduct scenarios described in Section 2.6.2. Hence, the VIAD-DRONE take-off pose must be such that the pillar is within the field-of-view of the 2D LiDAR. This hypothesis does not impose any significant constraints apart from requiring sufficiently high range measuring requirements for the 2D LiDAR.
- VIAD-DRONE uses a configuration with non-tilled rotors in which stable flight involves that the robot *Roll* and *Pitch* angles can be assumed close to zero. This is a common assumption in many aerial robot perception systems. This assumption enables simplifying the 6-DoF pose estimation problem to a 4 DoF pose estimation problem.
- The value of the VIAD-DRONE *Yaw* angle along the mission must be limited between -90 to 90 degrees w.r.t. the orientation of the viaduct. The 2D LiDAR suffers from occlusions caused by the mirror and the robot body itself, see Section 2.6.4. To ensure that the 2D LiDAR measurements from the pillar are obtained with no occlusions, the pillar must always be within its the field-of-view, hence VIAD-DRONE must have a *Yaw* angle along the mission between -90 to 90 degrees.
- The drone-deck LiDAR measurements are used for drone altitude estimation. To avoid the need of knowing the inclination of the viaduct deck, we are assuming that the deck in the area of the full inspection mission (area where the drone navigates in the mission) is horizontal and parallel to the XY plane of the relative local reference frame at the take-off. This simplification can be avoided if the deck inclination is assumed known prior to the mission.

The above hypotheses are general, and don't constrain, the scenario. The viaduct scenario will include, the scenario pillar and deck, but there are not any assumptions on the surrounding of the scenario. Of course, the only assumption is that the scenario is sufficiently clear of obstacles to enable drone navigation and prevent significant LiDAR measurement occlusions. Besides, most of the hypotheses refer to aspects that depend on the inspection mission itself, such as the initial take-off pose or the constraints on the *Yaw* angle, which depends on the occlusions of the 2D LiDAR caused by the VIAD-DRONE body, and hence depends on the arrangement of the LiDAR onboard the aerial robot. Apart from these hypotheses, the perception system and 6 DoF GNSS-free pose estimation method is general.

2.6.4 VIAD-DRONE aerial robot sensors

The VIAD-DRONE aerial robot was designed for operation in highly constrained environments including contact with the viaduct. This involves significant constraints in size and payload, which strongly constrain the sensors and the processing hardware that can be mounted on board. Instead of

a monolithic perception system based on a unique high-performance sensor, in the second period the perception system for VIAD-DRONE was redesigned to be based on fusing measurements from multi-modal sensors. This has the following advantages:

- **Reduction of weight** since it combines several lightweight sensors instead of one heavy sensor, reducing the overall onboard sensor weight.
- **Lower computational resources** since processing the measurements from one high-performance requires higher computational power than extracting from each type of sensors its contribution for the robot overall pose estimation.
- **Higher robustness** since the pose estimation is obtained from several different sensors instead of only one.

Figure 11 shows the exteroceptive perception sensor set-up used in VIAD-DRONE. This setup is completely different from the first initial set-up that was described in in D5.1, which was based on using a Total Station system. In the new approach, the drone has on board all the required sensors and processing. The VIAD-DRONE sensor setup includes:

- one camera pointing to the ground for relative localization via visual odometry (VO) in the X-Y plane,
- one laser altimeter to obtain absolute altitude measurements w.r.t. the ground,
- one 2D LiDAR set-up horizontally that gathers distance-range measurements between the robot and the pillar. Furthermore, a mirror is set to reflect some LiDAR beams upwards to the viaduct deck to provide measurements of the vertical distance between the robot and the deck.

Figure 11. VIAD-DRONE sensors setup.

2.6.5 GNSS-free 6 DoF pose estimation

Inspection of PILOTING infrastructures requires navigating near obstacles, and smooth and safe trajectories between the inspection points (waypoints) are necessary. For instance, scenarios such as viaducts deal with outdoor and high-altitude conditions such as wind gusts, positioning inaccuracies,

or being surrounded by obstacles. To facilitate the problem, we divided the localization problem into different stages for the envisioned inspection missions. This enables simplifying the problem and increasing the localization estimation accuracies. The adopted mission stages are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Stages of the viaduct inspection missions: *take off*, *navigation*, and *approach & contact*.

Each mission is divided in three stages: i) *take off*, ii) *navigation*, and iii) *approach & contact* (with the deck or the pillar). Depending on the mission stage, the processing of certain sensors is enabled/disabled, and some parameters of the processing methods will be changed. Module *Localization Manager* in Figure 13 is responsible for managing the transitions between stages, enabling/disabling the integration of sensors in the Kalman Filter (KF), and configuration of the parameters of the perception processing components, among others.

During the *take off* stage, the processing of the camera is disabled since its proximity to the ground prevents obtaining correct information. After taking-off, once the robot altitude is above a minimum altitude, the camera measurements become useful. Then, the mission stage is changed to *navigation* and the processing of the camera is enabled. If the distance of VIAD-DRON to the structure is below certain levels, the stage is changed to *approach & contact*. It is the most critical stage, during which the localization uncertainty should be minimized. The perception system has positive synergies since 2D LiDAR gathers more information of the environment when it is closer to the viaduct surface, enabling more accurate pose estimation. Also, during *approach & contact* the aerial robot suffers from strong vibrations caused by the physical interactions with the deck or with the pillar. To prevent disturbances in the processing of the images from the camera, the processing of the camera is disabled in the *approach & contact* stage.

Figure 13 shows the general scheme of the multi-sensor pose estimation system developed for VIAD-DRONE. The estimation method processes the measurements from the altimeter, IMU, camera, and 2D LiDAR and fuses the results of the processing using Kalman Filter (KF). The measurements from

the camera and the laser altimeter are processed altogether with a visual odometry method to obtain an estimate of the displacement of the robot in consecutive times. This displacement is fused with the IMU measurements and used in the Prediction stage of the KF. The 2D LiDAR is processed by detecting the viaduct deck and pillar to obtain measurements of the robot absolute location, which is used in the KF Update stage.

Figure 13. Scheme of the VIAD-DRONE pose estimation method.

The mission is specified as a set of waypoints that are defined using the general Robot Control System (gRCS) in a previously generated map. However, VIAD-DRONE is localized with respect to a local reference frame specified at the initial take-off pose, which is different from global reference frame of the map, see Figure 14. The entire mission design is performed using global map frame, hence, the aerial robot pose must be referred to this frame. The *Mission Manager* module is responsible for transforming the frame-based information, connecting interfaces. The *Mission Manager* module on board receives the frame transformation from gRCS, using the local frame position with respect to the global frame. Local frame is set manually in gRCS interface before starting the mission.

Figure 14. Viaduct global map represented in the gRCS interface with different frames.

2D LiDAR localization

One of the main problems when using the measurements of the 2D LiDAR for aerial robot localization in outdoors is the low amount of useful information provided in environments with low geometrical information (low density of potential features). Besides, vegetation in the scene generates irregular LiDAR point clouds with low density, which the point clouds originated by the viaduct deck and pillar have high point density.

The proposed approach solves the localization problem by assuming there are some fixed objects in the scene (viaduct pillar and deck) and estimating the movement of the aerial robot with respect to these objects. Different objects in the environment will produce different density in their point-clouds. First, a point-cloud clustering method is used to distinguish between the point clouds generated by different types of objects. We use point cloud segmentation using density clustering with the DBSCAN algorithm [6]. Some fixed objects (pillar and decks) will present high spatial point cloud density compared to other elements (e.g., vegetation) and this property is used for classification.

After clustering, each point cloud cluster is characterized by the centroid $C_m = (x^c, y^c)$ and orientation α^c of the main axis of the point cloud distribution. The orientation α^c can be computed as the orientation of the eigenvector of the point cloud cluster distribution that corresponds to the largest eigenvalue. The aerial robot takes an initial 2D LiDAR scan before take-off, clusterizes the point cloud, selects the clusters assigned as fixed objects and characterize each cluster with its centroid (x_0, y_0) and orientation α_0 . Along the trajectory, the aerial robot repeats the operation to obtain at each time k the characterization of the clusters corresponding to the fixed objects. The cluster at time k is characterized by its centroid (x_k, y_k) and orientation α_k . If more than two fixed objects are present in the scenario, an association process is necessary to match the clusters detected at time k with the initial clusters. Criteria based on minimum distance and point cloud density (estimated by the DBSCAN algorithm) are used. Finally, the aerial robot displacement from the initial time to time k can be simply computed as:

$$x_k = x^c - (x_0 \cos(\alpha_k - \alpha_0) - y_0 \sin(\alpha_k - \alpha_0))$$

$$y_k = y^c - (x_0 \sin(\alpha_k - \alpha_0) + y_0 \cos(\alpha_k - \alpha_0))$$

$$\theta_k = \alpha_k - \alpha_0$$

These simple expressions enable to obtain the robot position in the horizontal and robot *Yaw* orientation angle (x_k, y_k, θ_k) at each time k . Besides, by using density point cloud segmentation, there is no need to have previous knowledge of the types of objects present in the scene, enabling generalization w.r.t. the particularities of the scenario.

The z_k coordinate of the aerial robot position at time k is estimated using the 2D LiDAR beams reflected by an onboard mirror that impact on the bottom surface of the viaduct deck. These LiDAR impacts generate point-clouds shaped in a straight line. The straight line is detected using the Hough Transform [7], which estimates the polar parameters of a given 2D line. Given that any line is defined

by two parameters -the distance between the line and the reference frame ρ_k , and its orientation θ_k -, the distance between the aerial robot and the viaduct deck surface is measured by ρ_k . Being ρ_0 the initial robot-deck distance measured at take-off, the z_k coordinate of the aerial robot at time k along the mission is computed as:

$$z_k = \rho_0 - \rho_k$$

Visual Odometry (VO)

Our odometry estimates the incremental displacement of the robot in 2D horizontal coordinates between two consecutive frames and this displacement is back-projected using the altimeter measurement. Visual odometry allows us to compute the robot position estimation along a complete trajectory. However, VO provides an incremental localization. Using it for estimating the full trajectory results in accumulative error (i.e., drift).

Our VO method is based on [8] in which the odometry problem is simplified with a flat motion (i.e., constant altitude) and solved as a least mean square problem (i.e., $Ax = b$):

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & -y_1 & 1 & 0 \\ y_1 & x_1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta \\ \sin \theta \\ p_x \\ p_y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ y_2 \end{bmatrix},$$

where (x_1, y_1) and (x_2, y_2) are a pair of matched features detected in consecutive images (taken at time k and $k+1$) taken by the camera, and p_x , p_y , and θ is the incremental displacement between consecutive images in axes X , Y and Yaw angle. The least mean square problem finds the values of p_x , p_y , and θ that best fit with the matched features in consecutive images.

Our method based on [8] but increase the efficiency in feature extraction and matching to enable real-time operation as specified for PILOTING use cases. First, the corner detector selected for features extraction was Shi-Tomasi [9]. Shi-Tomasi is widely used due to its simplicity, efficiency, and robust performance. Also, feature matching problem is solved using Lucas-Kanade optical flow tracker [10]. Moreover, it should be noticed that the distribution of the features is highly dependent on the scene, hence, there may be regions on the image with low feature density. To homogenise the density, the image is divided in $M \times N$ grids. Given a grid, if the number of corners is lower than a certain threshold, new corners are calculated on this specific region.

Besides, our method integrates altitude measurements gathered by the altimeter (see Figure 13). The VO results in image plane coordinates (p_x , p_y , and θ) are back-projected as follows:

$$\frac{1}{Z} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta X \\ \Delta Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = K^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} p_x \\ p_y \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

where $(\Delta X, \Delta Y)$ is the aerial robot displacement in world coordinates, K is the camera matrix, (p_x, p_y, θ) is the robot displacement in pixel coordinates, and Z is the distance between the camera and the ground, which is measured with the laser altimeter.

This method does not integrate IMU information. Generally, IMU are noisy, have low precision, and their measurements are affected in presence of strong electromagnetic fields or metallic structures, which can usually be found in viaduct scenarios. This improvement increases the accuracy and robustness of the resulting estimates. However, autopilot IMU is fused into KF as reinforcement but assigning it with large covariance (high uncertainty) and only in the Prediction KF stage, which is less sensitive to errors than the Update KF stage.

Kalman Filter (KF)

The Kalman Filter (KF) is an optimal probabilistic algorithm used to estimate the state of a system based on model predictions and measurements. Our localization algorithms use an KF to fuse the results obtained from visual odometry (VO) and LiDAR localization. The results from the visual odometry and measurements of the IMU are used in the KF prediction stage. The results from the LiDAR localization are integrated in the Update stage of the KF.

Assuming x_k as the pose of the robot, u_k as the control action, and z_k as the poses computed from the LiDAR processing, the KF requires the system dynamic model $x_{k+1} = f(x_k, u_k)$ for the KF Prediction Stage and the observation model $z_{k+1} = h(x_k)$ for the KF Update stage. The dynamic model adopted assumes the robot moves with constant speed. The robot speed used in the KF Update stage fuses the IMU measurements together with the results from the visual odometry (VO) in such a way that the IMU measurements are used as a reinforcement. These measurements were fused considering a high covariance matrix to take into account the potentially high noise level in these scenarios. It should be noticed that the aerial robot moves slowly in this physical contact inspection missions. Despite its simplicity, the linear model is enough to obtain good estimates with low uncertainty under these slow-motion conditions.

The KF Update stage includes the processing of the 2D LiDAR. The KF Update stage can have significantly high computational cost in case of integrating the raw 2D LiDAR measurements. To reduce the computational cost and enable onboard on-time execution, the 2D LiDAR are first processed by the 2D LiDAR localization module to obtain intermediate results that can be integrated very efficiently in the KF. As a result, the observation model used in the KF Update stage is a simple matrix, i.e. the LiDAR-based localization are directly correlated with the current robot state, without any transformation or scaling. In other words, the observation model assumes the LiDAR-based localization is in the same reference frame as the state estimation of the robot. The use of an identity matrix observation model simplifies the implementation of the KF and reduces computational complexity. Additionally, this assumption is valid in scenarios where the robot is moving slowly, and the LiDAR measurements are reliable and accurate. Therefore, the simplicity of the observation model combined with reliable LiDAR measurements allows for good state estimates with low uncertainty.

Both (system dynamics and observation) models are assumed under uncertainty modelled as AWGN noise with zero mean and covariance matrices. The resulting KF integrates multi-sensor measurements in a computationally efficient way to obtain accurate and robust robot pose localization estimates along the full trajectory avoiding the visual odometry drift.

2.6.6 Validation

The proposed VIAD-DRONE pose estimation method was experimented in real scenarios (viaduct at “Arroyo del Espinazo” in Álora, Spain) performing actual missions commanded by the gRCS. A wide number of experiments were conducted to test the robustness and repeatability of the results. In these experiments the ground truth localization was measured with a Total Station system. The Total Station does not provide the aerial robot orientation. However, the orientation of the aerial robot system affects its localization and hence, the goodness of the developed pose estimation method can be evaluated only from the assessment of its 3D localization.

Figure 15 shows the VIAD-DRONE 3D localization results in one full mission VS the ground truth obtained with a Total Station system in one of the tenths of experiment conducted at “Arroyo del Espinazo” viaduct in Álora, Spain. The errors in the three axes are in the range of cms. The errors in axis Z were particularly low, as result of the integration of two altitude measurements, one from the altimeter and the other, from the LiDAR equipped with the mirror. This effect is very interesting in robots that must establish and keep contact with the viaduct deck as physical contact interactions require very low robot localization errors. The errors in axis Y, the direction along the viaduct main axis, were also very low. This is result of the high amount of information provided by the 2D LiDAR measurements sensing the viaduct pillar. Also, this effect is very interesting in robots that must establish contact with the viaduct pillar in *target installation* missions. Target installation requires physical contact with the pillar, which again needs very low errors and high robustness. The highest error is obtained in axis X, perpendicular to the viaduct main axis. The error is not as high since the 2D LiDAR measurements have lower information content in this axis. The error level in this axis is not so critical since it is not directly involved in physical contact operations. In any case, the mean error in this axis in all the performed experiments was lower than 12 cm, which was sufficiently low to onboard close the control loop of the aerial robots and safely enable aerial robot navigation in the unstructured and complex PILOTING viaduct scenarios.

Figure 15. VIAD-DRONE 6 DoF localization estimation results in one full mission VS the ground truth obtained with a Total Station system in one experiment conducted at “Arroyo del Espinazo” viaduct in Álora, Spain.

Table 1 summarizes mean performance metrics of the develop pose estimation system considering all the conducted experiments in real viaduct scenarios. It shows the maximum, average and standard deviation errors of the X, Y, and Z axes along the full experiment. These errors were calculated by comparing the estimated position of the robot with the ground truth position provided with a Total Station system. The average error for the X axis was 0.12 m, while for the Y and Z axes it was 0.06 m and 0.08 m, respectively. The maximum error for the X axis was 0.27 meters, and for the Y and Z axes it was 0.16 meters and 0.19 meters, respectively. The standard deviation for the X axis was 0.06 meters, for the Y axis it was 0.027 meters, and for the Z axis it was 0.034 meters.

Table 1. Average and maximum errors and standard deviation of the error of the VIAD-DRONE 3D localization along the full trajectory in the conducted experiments in different viaducts including the “Arroyo del Espinazo” viaduct.

	e_{max}	e_{mean}	e_{σ}
X-axis	0.27 m	0.12 m	0.06 m
Y-axis	0.16 m	0.06 m	0.027 m
Z-axis	0.19 m	0.08 m	0.034 m

These results provide important information about the high accuracy of the robot autonomous navigation obtained with our proposed localization method. This accuracy level was observed in every of the conducted experiments (more than 20) showing significant robustness. Besides, these results were obtained on board and in real time requiring moderate computational cost. In fact, this pose estimation is used by VIAD-DRONE to onboard and in real-time close the trajectory following and control loop.

2.7 Tunnel local inspection

2.7.1 Introduction

The tunnel inspection involves the use of two types of robots, namely the UGV (Unmanned Ground Vehicle) and the TTDRONE (Tunnel Tethered DRONE) aerial robot. While the UGV is responsible for the general inspection of the tunnel, the TTDRONE is responsible for the local inspection, providing a closer view of the inspection points. The TTDRONE is connected to the UGV through a tethered system, which enables power supply and data transmission between the two robots. The TTDRONE tethered system is described in deliverable D4.3. In this use case the tunnel inspection is performed combining both robots. The UGV moves along the tunnel and stops at points of interest where potential defects have been previously detected, while the aerial robot takes accurate measurements of these defects, hence inspecting the tunnel at locations that cannot be accessed by the ground robot. For safety reasons, while the UGV moves, the aerial robot is kept static to the take-off/landing pad on top of the UGV roof using electromagnets. Electromagnets are deactivated when the ground robot stops, and the aerial robot is about to take off. The information about both robots can be found in project deliverable D4.3.

2.7.2 Tunnel inspection missions

The aerial robot (TTDRONE) starts the mission by taking off from the starting point, located on the roof of the ground robot. Then, the robot autonomously navigates following waypoints to reach inspection points. The aerial robot stops at each inspection point and takes pictures of the defects of interest, which enables the detailed visual assessment of the tunnel. The defect images should be captured at a specific distance from the tunnel surface. This distance is estimated to provide an appropriate level of detail for the best performance of the AI detection algorithms. The camera has gimbal-stabilization to compensate the aerial robot vibrations while capturing images. Finally, the robot navigates back and finally autonomously lands on the UGV. The aerial robot receives the energy supply from the UGV through the tether system, being capable of achieving flight durations that cannot be achieved using batteries. Figure 16 shows a typical tunnel inspection mission performed by TTDRONE. The shown picture was taken in the experiments performed in Metsovo tunnel, in Greece.

Figure 16. Typical mission of TTDRONE in tunnel inspection. Picture taken in experiments conducted in Metsovo tunnel in Greece.

2.7.3 Hypotheses of the VIAD-DRONE GNSS-free 6-DoF pose estimation

Due to tunnel characteristics and the synchronization between the UGV and the aerial robot, some assumptions are adopted to increase general safety and pose estimation accuracy:

- The TTDRONE take-off and landing position is the same and is located on the UGV roof. The electromagnets must be activated while the UGV is in motion to prevent changes in the TTDRONE take-off and landing pose.
- The localization system estimates the TTDRONE pose in a coordinate frame relative to the take-off and landing pose. Before the start of the TTDRONE mission, it receives from the UGV the UGV position in tunnel global coordinates of the environment map. This is used to transform the TTDRONE position to the tunnel global coordinates.
- TTDRONE always takes off and lands once the UGV is inside the tunnel. The localization method needs information from the tunnel section (plane transversal to the tunnel main axis) to estimate the position.
- The TTDRONE can only perform autonomous taking-off and landing if the UGV is static and is located on a horizontal area. For safety reasons, the aerial robot will only take-off/land if the UGV is static and the landing pad (on the UGV roof) is horizontal.
- Tunnel walls are assumed to be planar. The localization method matches the 2D LiDAR point cloud with planar surfaces. This assumption has been considered due to the characteristics of the most frequent tunnels where the PILOTING inspection is envisioned, including the Metsovo tunnel, the final PILOTING tunnel scenario. Extending these inspections to curved wall tunnels requires a slightly modified version of the localization method to adapt the point cloud matching method.
- The tunnel must not have significant irregularities that strongly modify its geometry.

- TTDRONE uses a configuration with non-tilled rotors in which stable flight involves that the robot *Roll* and *Pitch* angles can be assumed close to zero. This is a common assumption in many aerial robot perception systems. This assumption enables simplifying the 6-DoF pose estimation problem to a 4 DoF pose estimation problem.

The above hypotheses do not constrain the specified operation for PILOTING tunnel inspections. The method assumes no previous information on the scenario except that fact that tunnels have planar surfaces. However, it can be easily extended to tunnels with curved walls. Of course, the scenario must be sufficiently clear to enable drone navigation and significant levels of LiDAR occlusions.

2.7.4 TTDRONE aerial robot sensors

The TTDRONE aerial robot was designed for operation in highly constrained tunnel environments. This involves significant constraints in size and payload, which strongly constrain the sensors and the processing hardware that can be mounted on board. Instead of a monolithic perception system based on a unique high-performance sensor, the perception system of TTDRONE includes several multi-modal sensors, which provide advantages in terms of reduction of weight, lower computational resources, and higher robustness.

TTDRONE should localize w.r.t. the UGV. The UGV uses its own localization system and is capable of globally self-localizing in the tunnel global coordinate system. TTDRONE should include sensors to enable its relative localization w.r.t. the take-off position, which is located on the roof of the UGV. The absolute location of the UGV can be easily obtained by transforming the TTDRONE relative pose w.r.t. the take-off position on the UGV roof with respect to the global tunnel coordinate system by using the UGV localization in global coordinates. That way TTDRONE will reference the defect images it captures in the tunnel global tunnel coordinates. Hence, our problem from a localization perspective is to compute the pose estimations of TTDRONE w.r.t. its take-off/landing pose on the UGV roof.

Figure 17 shows the exteroceptive perception sensor set-up used in TTDRONE. The first sensor setup described in deliverable D5.1, which was mainly based on visual cameras, was found to have insufficient robustness against occlusions originated by the UGV and the tether system itself. Hence, the sensor selection, setup, and involved processing, has been re-designed in the last period to reduce uncertainty and increase robustness. The final TTDRONE sensor setup includes:

- one 2D LiDAR, which sensing plane is transversal to the main axis of the tunnel. It is called LiDAR1. The measurements from LiDAR1 are processed to obtain the robot localization in the plane transversal to the tunnel main axis.
- one 2D LiDAR with horizontal sensing plane. It is called LiDAR2. The measurements from LiDAR2 are processed to obtain the *Yaw* of the aerial robot w.r.t. the direction of the tunnel main axis.
- one UWB beacon that estimates the robot location w.r.t. four UWB beacons located on the UGV, see Figure 17-right.

Figure 17. Left) Setup of TTDRONE in tunnel inspection. Right) Setup of the four UWB beacons on UGV used for TTDRONE localization.

A scheme showing the measurements gathered by the TTDRONE localization sensors is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Scheme showing the tunnel measurements gathered by the TTDRONE localization sensors.

2.7.5 GNSS-free 6 DoF pose estimation

Figure 19 shows the general scheme of the multi-sensor pose estimation system developed for TTDRONE. It processes the measurements from the two 2D LiDAR and from the beacons and integrates the results of both processing modules using a Kalman Filter (KF). The *Beacon-based Localization* module integrates the range measurements between the UWB beacon on TTDRONE and the UWB beacons on top of the UGV. The LiDAR scans from LiDAR1 and LiDAR2 are processed by the *LiDAR-based Localization* module. The results of both types of processing are integrated in the Update Stage of the KF.

Figure 19. Scheme of the TTDRONE pose estimation method.

The mission is specified as a set of waypoints that are defined using the general Robot Control System (gRCS) in a previously generated map. TTDRONE is localized with respect to a local reference frame specified at the initial take-off pose, which is different from global reference frame of the map, see Figure 20. Like in the viaduct scenario, the entire mission design is performed using global map frame, hence, the aerial robot pose must be referred to this frame. The *Mission Manager* module is responsible for transforming the frame-based information, connecting interfaces.

Figure 20. Tunnel global map represented in the gRCS interface with different frames.

In next subsections the main processing components in the TTDRONE pose estimation method are described.

Beacon-based localization

Beacon sensors allow to estimate the distance from a transmitter node to a receptor node combining Ultra-Wideband (UWB) and inertial measurement unit (IMU) technologies to provide indoor localization. UWB is a wireless technology that uses a large swath of the radio spectrum to transmit data over short distances. The key feature of UWB is its ability to accurately measure distance and

location by calculating the time delay between the transmission of a signal and its reception. UWB transmits signals with a very short duration and a large bandwidth, which results in high time resolution and allows for accurate distance measurements. The signals are typically transmitted using a pulse-based modulation scheme, which allows for easy detection and demodulation.

Mathematically, UWB localization is based on the principle of time-of-flight (ToF) measurement. The time it takes a signal to travel from a transmitter to a receiver is proportional to the distance between them. The ToF is calculated by measuring the time delay between the transmission of a signal and its reception at a receiver. Since the speed of light is constant, the distance between the transmitter and the receiver can be calculated by multiplying the ToF by the speed of light. To estimate the position of a robot using UWB, multiple UWB transceivers are placed at known locations, known as anchors. The robot is equipped with a UWB transceiver that transmits signals to the anchors and receives signals back from them. The distances between the robot and the anchors can be calculated using the ToF measurements, and these distances can be used to triangulate the position of the robot. This process is known as trilateration and can be expressed mathematically as:

$$d_i = ||p - a_i|| + n_i$$

where d_i is the measured distance between the robot and the i -th anchor, p is the position of the robot, a_i is the position of the i -th anchor, and n_i is the measurement noise.

By measuring the distances to at least three anchors, the position of the robot p can be estimated using trilateration. This results in the intersection point of three spheres with radii equal to the distances to the reference points. To improve the accuracy of the position estimate, more anchors can be added, and the distances to these anchors can be used to refine the position estimate using techniques such as multi-lateration or least squares optimization.

In PILOTING we use 4 beacon emitters (see Figure 17) to solve the problem with an overdetermined system, resulting in higher precision. The resulting estimate is used as input of the EKF that integrates these measurements with the result of 2D LIDAR. Instead of using multilateration or least squares optimization, we estimated the robot position using an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF). EKF provides optimal state estimates in presence of Gaussian noise. The beacon range measurements are integrated in the EKF Update stage, as in [11]. The EKF state is defined as the robot position in the local reference frame. Since range measurements are non-linear, the EKF uses the Jacobian matrices of the observation models. The state prediction model used in the EKF Prediction stage predicts the robot location at time $k+1$ using the robot estimated location at time k and the robot motion measured with the IMU. It is a simple model, which reduces the computational cost of other more complex aerial robot kinematic models and is sufficiently accurate for the desired levels of accuracy. Although computing the aerial robot position only from the IMU would result in drift, using the UWB in the EKF Update stage cancels the effect of the drift and enables accurate long-term localization accuracy.

LiDAR-based localization

Two 2D LiDARs have been used in TTDRONE. LiDAR2 is positioned horizontally. Its sensing plane is horizontal. It gathers measurements of the impact of the beam of LiDAR2 on the tunnel walls. As the tunnel walls are assumed to be straight, the generated point-cloud is distributed along two straight lines in the horizontal plane, each of them caused by the LiDAR2 reflections on one tunnel wall. The aerial robot *Yaw* angle is obtained using these measurements.

First, these lines are detected. The RANdom SAMple Consensus (RANSAC) algorithm is used [12]. RANSAC works by randomly selecting a minimal subset of data points and estimating the parameters of a model using only those points. The model is then evaluated by counting the number of data points that agree with the model within a certain tolerance threshold. If the number of inliers exceeds a predefined threshold, the estimated model is considered valid and is then re-estimated using all inliers. This process is repeated multiple times, and the best model is selected based on the number of inliers it produces.

RANSAC is used to fit a model to the point cloud inliers. The model is described by a set of parameters, denoted by θ . Mathematically, we can describe the fitting process as:

$$\arg \max_{\theta} \sum_i w(i) I(\text{dist}(i, \theta) < \text{threshold})$$

where θ represents the model parameters, $w(i)$ is a weight assigned to each data point, $\text{dist}(i, \theta)$ is the distance between the data point i and the model defined by θ , and $I(\text{dist}(i, \theta) < \text{threshold})$ is an indicator function that returns 1 if the distance is lower than a threshold, and 0 otherwise. The *argmax* function returns the set of model parameters that maximizes the number of inliers.

Hence, to detect a line in a point-cloud using RANSAC, we follow these steps:

1. Randomly select two points from the point cloud.
2. Compute the parameters of the line between these two points.
3. Count the number of points that lie close enough to this line (using a predefined threshold).
4. Repeat steps 1-3 a fixed number of times.
5. Select the line with the most inliers (i.e., the highest count from step 3).
6. Recompute the parameters of the line using all the inliers found in step 5.

The parameters of the line can be expressed in different ways depending on the chosen coordinate system. One possible representation is the slope-intercept form:

$$y = mx + b,$$

where m is the slope, and b is the y-intercept. Given two points (x_1, y_1) and (x_2, y_2) , the slope and y-intercept can be computed as:

$$m = \frac{(y_2 - y_1)}{(x_2 - x_1)} \quad b = y_1 - m * x_1$$

The slope of the line, m , determines the angle α_k between the X axis of the robot local reference frame and the tunnel main axis at time k in which the scan from LiDAR2 was captured. Let α_0 be the angle between the X axis of the robot local reference frame and the tunnel main axis at the take-off time. As the aerial robot take-off pose is taken as the origin of the tunnel local reference frame, the robot Yaw angle at time k expressed in the tunnel local reference frame can be simply computed as:

$$\theta_k = \alpha_k - \alpha_0$$

The other LiDAR sensor installed on TTDRONE is LiDAR1, which is positioned vertically and perpendicularly to the main tunnel axis and is used to estimate the aerial robot position in the tunnel cross-section. Its sensing plane is perpendicular to the tunnel main axis. It allows obtaining the cross-section of the tunnel and determining the aerial robot position relative to this section. In this case the point cloud is fit to the tunnel roof, which follows a circular shape. The tunnel roof is parametrized with a circle model and fit using RANSAC:

$$(x - a)^2 + (y - b)^2 = r^2$$

where r is the radius of the circumference and a and b are the coordinates of the centre of the circumference expressed in the aerial robot local coordinate system.

Let a_0 and b_0 as the coordinates of the centre of the circumference in the aerial robot local coordinate system when the aerial robot at the take-off pose, i.e. when the robot was at the origin of the tunnel local reference frame. Let a_k and b_k as the coordinates of the centre of the circumference in the aerial robot local coordinate system at time k along the mission. It is not difficult to notice that the position of the aerial robot at time k in the tunnel cross-section plane expressed in the tunnel local reference frame (i.e., plane YZ) can be simply computed as:

$$y_k = a_k - a_0$$

$$z_k = b_k - b_0$$

Hence, the processing of LiDAR1 provides by using the above simple expressions the position of the aerial robot in plane YZ in the tunnel local reference frame.

Kalman Filter (KF)

We use a Kalman Filter (KF) to fuse and smooth the localization estimates obtained from LiDAR1 (in the cross-section plane), LiDAR2 (Yaw angle) and the beacon-based localization. All these estimates are expressed in the same time k and the same reference frame, the tunnel local reference frame defined by the aerial robot take-off pose on top of the UGF roof.

The KF update stage uses the localization estimates obtained by the processing of LiDAR1, LiDAR2 and the beacons. For such integration each estimate is assigned with a covariance matrix, which was assigned from previous experiments performed in the Coripe tunnel in Sevilla province. In these

experiments we noticed that the processing the LiDAR1 and LiDAR2 provided very accurate estimates (mean lower than 15 cm) while the beacon-based localization generated a bit greater errors (mean of 30 cm). A higher covariance matrix was assigned to the beacon measurements, as these can be particularly noisy at the start of the mission. In the KF Prediction stage, we used a static motion model. The robot motion is slow and smooth during the mission. Hence, using a static robot motion is not misleading and has an overall smoothing effect. The prediction model was assigned with a significantly high covariance matrix, to enable a trade-off between the desired smoothing effect and the influence of the robot localization estimates provided by the LIDAR1, LIDAR2 and beacon measurements. That way we keep the KF computationally efficient and suitable in terms of smoothing properties and accuracy.

2.7.6 Validation

The proposed TTDRONE pose estimation method was experimented in real scenarios, namely Metsovo tunnel in Greece and Coripe tunnel in the province of, Spain). The experiments were conducted performing actual missions commanded by the gRCS. In these experiments the ground truth localization was measured with a Total Station system, which enabled assessing the localization accuracy of the method. The Total Station does not provide the aerial robot orientation. However, the orientation of the aerial robot system affects its localization and hence, the goodness of the developed pose estimation method can be evaluated only from the assessment of its 3D localization.

Figure 21 shows the TTDRONE 3D localization results in one full mission VS the ground truth obtained with a Total Station system in one of the tenths of experiment conducted at Metsovo tunnel in Greece. The errors in the three axes are in the range of cms. The errors in axis Z were particularly low, as result of the integration of the measurements from LiDAR1, which enables estimating the aerial robot location on the tunnel cross-section with very low error.

Figure 21. TTDRONE localization estimation results in one full mission VS the ground truth obtained with a Total Station system in one experiment conducted at Metsovo tunnel, Spain.

The errors in axis X , the other coordinate together with axis Z on the tunnel cross-section, were also very low. This is motivated by the high information level in the measurements from LiDAR1 for estimating the aerial robot location on the tunnel cross-section. The highest error is obtained in axis X , which corresponds to the tunnel main axis. The main contribution for the estimation in this axis come from the beacon localization. The beacon range measurements in indoor scenarios with high density of metallic structures and objects, such as tunnels, have a certain level of noise. Although the EKF that integrates the beacon measurements cancels some of this noise, it cannot cancel it all resulting in some error in the robot position estimate. In any case, the mean error in this axis in all the performed experiments was lower than 20 cm, which was sufficiently low to onboard close the control loop of the aerial robots and safely enable aerial robot navigation in unstructured and complex scenarios, such as the PILOTING tunnel scenarios.

Table 2 summarizes mean performance metrics of the develop pose estimation system considering all the conducted experiments in real tunnel scenarios. It shows the maximum, average and standard deviation errors of the X , Y , and Z axes along the full mission. These errors were calculated by comparing the estimated position of the robot with the ground truth position provided with a Total Station system. The average error for the X axis was 0.08 m, while for the Y and Z axes it was 0.21 m and 0.13 m, respectively. The maximum errors along the missions are also shown. The standard deviation for the X axis was 0.07 m, for the Y axis it was 0.11 m, and for the Z axis it was 0.1 m.

Table 2. Average and maximum errors and standard deviation of the error of the TTDRONE 3D localization along the full trajectory in the conducted experiments in different tunnels including the Metsovo tunnel in Greece.

	e_{max}	e_{mean}	e_{σ}
X-axis	0.23 m	0.08 m	0.07 m
Y-axis	0.45 m	0.21 m	0.11 m
Z-axis	0.30 m	0.13 m	0.1 m

This accuracy level was observed in every of the conducted experiments (more than 30) showing significant robustness. Besides, these results were obtained on board and in real time requiring moderate computational cost. In fact, this pose estimation is used by TTDRONE to onboard and in real-time close the trajectory following and control loops.

3. Aerial interaction control

This section presents the control architecture used in the PILOTING aerial robots for achieving stability and control of their contact operations. As it is described in D4.3, in PILOTING there are several aerial robots that have been developed for operation in the viaduct, tunnel and refinery inspection use cases that require to maintain contact while flying. A general control structure has been defined that is used by all the aerial robots in the project.

Figure 22. PILOTING control structure.

The general control structure used in the PILOTING aerial robots is presented in Figure 22. The Localization block is responsible of the estimation of the state of the aerial robot $\hat{\xi}, \hat{\xi}$ and has been presented in Section 2. This estimation is fed back to the different blocks to close the control loop. The Mission block parses the mission commands communicated by the gRCS to the other blocks. The Trajectory Generator is responsible of managing the waypoints and generating specific trajectories for the approach to surface and depart operations, obtaining the references for the position and attitude controllers. These two blocks (Position Controller and Attitude Controller) are the responsible for obtaining the three torque and the vertical force input values for real time control of the aerial robot, which are fed to the Mixer and then to the motors of the Aerial Robot. The Control Manager is responsible for the management of the different operating modes of the robots during inspection in the PILOTING use cases. The different blocks of the control structure will be explained in the following subsections.

3.1 Implementation of the Control Manager

When performing an inspection mission, aerial robots find different conditions and control needs in the different phases of the mission. In a typical inspection mission with contact the following phases can be defined:

1. Take-off.

2. Go to inspection point (separated more than 2 m from surfaces, free flight)
3. Approach flight (separated less than 2 m from the surfaces)
4. Establish contact with the surface
5. Maintain contact
6. Release contact from the surface
7. Separate from the surface, go to 2) if another inspection point in the plan
8. Go back to home (free flight)
9. Landing

Phases 1 and 9 are for the take-off and landing, which can be done autonomously or assisted by the pilot. In phase 2 (and 8) the aerial robot flies in free flight, with enough separation from the different surfaces of the inspected asset. In phases 3 and 7, the robot has to approach or separate from the surface following a specified trajectory to avoid collisions and facilitate contact phases. Phases 4 to 6 (contact phases) are the most critical from the safety point of view, they imply significant changes in the dynamics of the aerial robot and high control requirements. In phase 5 the contact position can be maintained for a given time, or it can be moved along the surface.

Figure 23. State machine with the different phases in PILOTING aerial robots.

The different phases of the mission are implemented in the aerial robot controller with a Finite State Machine (FSM) as shown in Figure 23. Each state corresponds to a different phase with their own control objectives and control structure. The transitions between the states are triggered by different conditions defined by the mission control (for example, initiate phase 1), or the localization system (for example, transition from phase 2 to phase 3). The transitions in the contact phases are critical, and a contact observer and force observer are used.

3.2 Position and attitude controllers

This section describes the implementation of the controllers in the PILOTING aerial robots. As they operate in different environments and with or without physical interaction, general modular controllers were defined in D5.1 for the PILOTING aerial robots. The controllers are based on the dynamic model for a multicopter and a k -link manipulator arm, which can be expressed in general form as:

$$M(\xi)\ddot{\xi} + C(\xi, \dot{\xi})\dot{\xi} + G(\xi) = F_{prop}(\xi) + F_{ext} + F_{cont} \quad (1)$$

where the generalized coordinates are defined as $\xi = [p \ \eta \ \gamma]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$, with $n = 6 + k$; where $p = [x \ y \ z]^T$ represents the translation coordinates of the multirotor center of gravity relative to the inertial frame, $\eta = [\phi \ \theta \ \psi]^T$ describes the vehicle attitude and $\gamma = [\gamma_1 \ \gamma_2 \ \dots \ \gamma_k]^T$ are the joint angles of the arm. Here, M is the inertia matrix, the Coriolis and centrifugal terms are represented by C and the gravitational force terms are described by G . Vector $F_{prop}(\xi)$ encompasses actuator forces and torques exerted by the propellers. External forces and moments are represented by F_{ext} , which include aerodynamic interference, wind and other atmospheric perturbations, and F_{cont} , which include the contact forces and moments of the end effector with the structure surfaces that it is inspecting.

As defined in D5.1, the general form of the integral backstepping controller for attitude control is:

$$U_\eta = M_\eta [K_1 e_\eta + K_2 \dot{e}_\eta + K_3 \chi_\eta + \ddot{\eta}_d] + C_\eta + G_\eta - \tilde{M}_{\eta\gamma} \ddot{\gamma} - \tilde{M}_\eta \ddot{\eta} - \tilde{\tau}_c \quad (2)$$

Where the attitude input control vector is $U_\eta = [U_\phi \ U_\theta \ U_\psi]^T$, e_η is the tracking error, \dot{e}_η the angular velocity tracking error and χ_η the integral of the angular position tracking error. The matrix $C_\eta \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and is the lower part of the Coriolis and centrifugal forces vector. The terms $\tilde{M}_\eta \ddot{\eta}$ and $\tilde{M}_{\eta\gamma} \ddot{\gamma}$ introduce the estimation of the dynamic coupling and $\tilde{\tau}_c$ the estimation of the torque induced by the contact force, F_E .

Now, if U_x and U_y are defined as the virtual position control inputs for the XY position controller, the position controller can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} U_z &= \frac{m}{\cos \phi \sin \theta} [g + K_z e_z + K_z \dot{e}_z + L_z \chi_z + \ddot{z}_d] - \tilde{F}_{E_z} \\ U_x &= \frac{m}{U_z} [K_x e_x + K_x \dot{e}_x + L_x \chi_x + \ddot{x}_d] - \tilde{F}_{E_x} \\ U_y &= -\frac{m}{U_z} [K_y e_y + K_y \dot{e}_y + L_y \chi_y + \ddot{y}_d] - \tilde{F}_{E_y} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The detailed expression of the controllers for the different PILOTING aerial robot can be found in D5.1.

Aerodynamic interaction effects appear when the multirotor is flying close to the ground, the ceiling or other surfaces, the rotor thrust and drag model are no longer valid, due to the aerodynamic effects. To account for these effects, the standard thrust model is modified as: $T = T_n + T_a(\xi)$, where $T_a(\xi)$ is the additional thrust due to aerodynamic effects, which depends on the relative position of the rotors with respect to the surfaces in the environment. These effects have been studied and modelled in PILOTING for the viaduct and tunnel scenarios [13] [14].

3.3 Trajectory generation

In phase 3 “Approach flight” and phase 7 “Separate from surface” it is very important to precisely control the position and velocity of the aerial robot to avoid collisions and attain good conditions for the establish contact phase. For that purpose, a safe approach trajectory is defined. In absence of other obstacles, the approach trajectory will be a straight path normal to the surface. If there are obstacles or other surfaces close to the contact point, the trajectory can be created by trajectory generation methods as potential fields and pseudospectral collocation.

Then, the following procedure is done in the controller for phases 3 and 7:

1. Define the contact point in the surface of the viaduct or tank that we want to inspect (\vec{X}_0). This point is given by the mission control.
2. Define an approach trajectory that ends in the contact point, which will be normal to the surface in the contact point. The straight path can be defined in vector form as: \vec{X}_0
3. Use a trajectory tracking controller for the approach flight.

In PILOTING we have implemented a 3D modified pure pursuit trajectory tracking controller with velocity adaptation. The procedure for a straight path is explained below.

If $\vec{X}_0 = [x_0 \ y_0 \ z_0]^T$ is the point in the surface where we want the robot to attain contact with its end effector, the equation of the straight path normal to the surface at this point is: $\vec{X} = \vec{X}_0 + \lambda \vec{d}$, with \vec{d} the director vector normal to the surface.

If \vec{Q} is the actual position of the robot at each time instant, the vector $\vec{P} = \vec{Q} - \vec{X}_0$ points from the robot position to the contact point. Its projection on the path normal to the contact point is given by \vec{Q}_P :

$$t = \frac{\vec{d} \cdot \vec{P}}{\|\vec{d}\|} \quad , \quad \vec{Q}_P = \vec{X}_0 + t\vec{d} \quad (4)$$

Then the lookahead distance α is added along the straight path to get the goal point to which the aerial robot should be directed:

$$\vec{Q}_L = \vec{Q}_P + \alpha \vec{d} \quad (5)$$

Finally, the commanded velocity direction of the aerial robot is given by:

$$\vec{v}_c = \frac{\vec{Q}_L - \vec{Q}}{\|\vec{Q}_L - \vec{Q}\|} \quad (6)$$

The modulus of the velocity is adapted when it is approaching the contact point using the distance to the pillar D measured by the local localization system:

$$\|\vec{v}\|_c = K_P D \quad (7)$$

With K_p a proportional gain.

3.4 Dynamic and control constraints

When the aerial robot is in contact with the surfaces of the viaduct or the tank, there is a change in its dynamics so that some movements are restricted. When the end effector is in contact or sliding over the surface, the movement of the end effector is constrained in the direction normal to the surface and direction towards the surface.

Figure 24. Aerial robot in contact with: a) pillar (vertical surface); b) beam (horizontal surface).

Figure 24 shows a PILOTING aerial robot in contact with vertical and horizontal surfaces. In these cases, the controller structure gets constrained as follows:

- Contact with a vertical surface: the contact with the surface imposes the constraints that the position of the end effector in the direction normal to the surface $x_B = const$, and also the pitch and yaw angles are $\theta = const$, $\psi = const$. Thus, during the pillar contact, the x , θ and ψ controllers should be disabled and $F_x = const > 0$, and $\tau_\theta = \tau_\psi = 0$ are imposed.
- Contact with a horizontal surface: the contact with the horizontal surface imposes the constraints that the vertical position $z = const$ and the pitch and roll angles get also fixed, $\theta = const$ and $\varphi = const$. Thus, when the contact is active the altitude, pitch and roll controllers should be disabled, and $F_z = mg + \Delta F_z$ with $\Delta F_z > 0$, and $\tau_\theta = \tau_\varphi = 0$ are imposed.

These constraints are present in phase 5 “Maintain contact”, while in phase 4 and 6 they have to be switched on and off maintaining the stability of the aerial robot. All these operations are performed by the Control Manager in Figure 22.

3.5 External wrench observer

In aerial manipulation and operations that require contact of the aerial robots with the environment it is very important for stabilization and control of the flying robots to know the interaction forces. This

may be provided by a dedicated force sensor, although it adds additional weight to the robot and cannot be included easily in small or medium size aerial robots.

A wrench observer is an estimator of the external forces and torques acting on a flying robot that exploit the control input, state measurements, and a dynamics model. The observer schemes more frequently used in aerial robots are the so-called momentum-based and acceleration-based approaches, which make direct use of the gyro and accelerometer sensor readings respectively.

A hybrid estimator that combines both approaches is well tailored to the needs of flying systems [15]. By considering the directly measurable values, the hybrid estimator combines the two methods, where the accelerometer-based method is used for external force estimation and the momentum-based method for external torque estimation. By combining both methods, we can estimate the external wrench using proprioceptive sensors only.

The resulting estimated external wrench $\hat{F}_{ext} = [\hat{f}_{ext} \quad \hat{\tau}_{ext}]^T$ has the following expression:

$$\hat{F}_{ext} = \begin{bmatrix} \int_0^t K_{If} (Ma - f - \hat{f}_{ext}) dt \\ K_{Im} (J\omega - \int_0^t (\tau + \tau_g + (J\omega) \times \omega - \hat{\tau}_{ext}) dt \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where the estimator gain K_I is split into its diagonal blocks K_{If} for the force and K_{Im} for the torque components, $a = R^T(\ddot{r} - g e_3)$ is the acceleration measured by an accelerometer in the body frame, τ_g is the torque due to the offset center of gravity, and $\hat{\tau}_{ext}$ is the estimated external torque, also expressed in the body frame. Note that an accelerometer also measures the acceleration of gravity. By combining both methods, we can estimate the external wrench using proprioceptive sensors only.

In PILOTING aerial robots two different instantiations of the wrench observer are used: the force observer for estimating contact forces when the aerial robot is maintaining contact with a surface, and the contact observer, to estimate the instant when the contact is established.

3.5.1 Force observer

Contact inspection while flying with the PILOTING aerial robots is done mainly with the VIAD-DRONE and AEROX robots. In both cases the contact surface is small and therefore the contact forces are much more significant than contact torques. In these cases, contact forces are relevant for the controller, and the force observer is used, this is, an observer that estimates the contact forces in the three axes. This force observer is relevant in phase 5 ‘‘Maintain contact’’ of the mission described above.

The force observer implemented in PILOTING aerial robots uses the structure presented above. The force observer has been implemented in the aerial robot described in [16] for viaduct inspection, which is a forerunner of the VIAD-DRONE used for testing control concepts (see Figure 25). The robot has a carbon fiber structure that allows it to attain and maintain contact with horizontal surfaces

(as the lower part of the beam), vertical surfaces (as the pillar surface) and horizontal and vertical surfaces at the same time (lower part of the beam and upper part of the pillar, for inspecting bearings). The robot has been used to test and refine the force and contact observers.

Figure 25. Viaduct inspection aerial robot used for testing and validating control concepts.

The force observer has been tested in two scenarios:

- **Beam Inspection:** For performing the beam inspection, the platform takes-off, goes to the references and performs the beam inspection. As the platform attains contact with the lower part of the beam during the inspection, the roll and pitch angles are imposed by the contact surface.

The results of an experiment in this case are shown in Figure 26, where the forces estimated in the three axes can be seen. Initially the aerial robot is in free flight until it comes into contact with the beam, around $t = 340$ s. Then, after the contact, a vertical force set point of -5 N is commanded while the robot slides along the surface maintaining the contact. Since the bottom of the beam where the experiment was done is slightly curved, the roll and pitch angles vary their values slightly with time.

Figure 26. Force observer in beam inspection, contact with horizontal surface: a) estimated forces; b) roll and pitch angles.

- **Bearing Inspection:** For the bearing inspection, the steps are similar to the beam inspection: the platform takes off, goes to the reference points and performs the bearing inspection. As the platform has contact with the vertical pillar surface, and with a horizontal plane, the beam surface, the X-position, Z-position, roll, pitch and yaw angles are imposed by the corner formed by the beam and pillar.

The results of an experiment in this case are shown in Figure 27, where the forces estimated in the three axes can be seen. Initially the aerial robot is in free flight until it comes into contact with the beam, around $t = 319$ s. A bit later at $t = 320$ s it also gets in contact with the pillar. After the contact with the corner, a vertical force of -5 N and a horizontal force of 2 N is maintained during several seconds.

Figure 27. Force observer in bearing inspection, simultaneous contact with horizontal and vertical surfaces: a) estimated forces; b) roll, pitch and yaw angles.

3.5.2 Contact observer

A special interesting case is to be able to detect the time instant the contact is produced since this will mark phase 4 “Establish contact”, and it is critical to maintain stability of the control system. For this purpose, the force observer presented in the previous section can be used with a smaller gain K_{If} . In PILOTING a modified index that uses the modulus of the sensed accelerations without gravity has been used:

$$\hat{I}_{cont} = M \|Ra + ge_3\| \quad (9)$$

This index is used only for detection of the contact, when the contact index goes above a predefined threshold, determined from the previous behavior of the index in free flight. Figure 28 shows the contact index for the beam inspection experiment presented above. In the figure it can be seen as the first contact is detected when it goes above the threshold.

Figure 28. Contact observer in beam inspection, contact with horizontal surface: a) contact index; b) contact detection.

The results of the contact detection for the simultaneous contact with beam and pillar are shown in Figure 29. It can be seen as the index detects the first contact with the lower part of the beam at $t = 319$ s. Then the robot slides along the beam surface until it gets in contact with the pillar at $t = 320$ s, which is also detected by the contact detection index.

Figure 29. Contact observer in bearing inspection, simultaneous contact with horizontal and vertical surfaces: a) contact index; b) contact detection.

3.6 Control structure of PILOTING aerial robots

As has been described in D4.3, in PILOTING five main aerial robots have been developed for the different use cases: AERO-CAM, HYBRID, TTDRONE, VIAD-DRONE and AEROX, shown in Figure 30. Each aerial robot will operate in different environmental conditions, some of them flying very close to surfaces and objects in the environment and with physical interaction. The control structure presented in the previous sections is adapted to the specific flight conditions of the different robots in the implementation of their controllers and autopilots.

Figure 30. PILOTING aerial robots: a) AERO-CAM; b) HYBRID; c) TTDRONE; d) VIAD-DRONE; e) AEROX.

The **AERO-CAM** (Figure 30a) flies separate from the different surfaces of the viaduct taking images, and thus no contact operation is needed. It uses a standard autopilot with waypoint guidance defined by the mission. A simplified list of phases and state machine without the contact phases (phases 3 to 7) is implemented in this robot. The attitude and position controllers will have the expressions presented in D5.1.

The operation of the **HYBRID** aerial robot (Figure 30b) is similar to the AERO-CAM since it has to fly from the initial point to the pipe it needs to inspect without approximating nor contacting any surface. Then it has to land on the pipe to perform the inspection with the crawler. So, the controller state machine for this robot will have phases 1, 2, 8 and 9. The Land phase will be different if landing on a pipe or landing at home at the end of the mission. When landing on a pipe, the Mission block will provide the waypoints to the landing point in the pipe, and then the Localization procedure described in Section 2.4 is used to guide the robot relative to the pipe until landing. For landing on a pipe, the controller developed in the HYFLIERS project has been adapted to the HYBRID aerial robot. The attitude and position controllers will have the expressions presented in D5.1.

TTDRONE (Figure 30c) missions involve successively visiting several waypoints to take measurements as explained in Section 2.7.2 and do not have contact operations. The state machine includes phases 1, 2, 8 and 9. The attitude and position controllers include the cable force, using the integral backstepping expression with the cable tension terms. The Localization block uses the 6D localization method w.r.t. the UGV explained in Section 2.7.5.

The missions of the **VIAD-DRONE** (shown in Figure 30d) have been described in Section 2.6, and involve contact with viaduct pillars in target installation and contact with the lower part of the beam in bearing inspection. Thus, the full control structure in Figure 22 and full state machine in Figure 23 are used in the aerial robot controller. The force and contact observers are both used in the different

phases and also the trajectory generator for the approach and depart phases. The Localization block uses the 6D pose estimation method presented in Section 2.6.5. The attitude and position controllers use the extended form including the contact and aerodynamic interaction terms, as explained in D5.1.

The **AEROX** aerial robot (Figure 30e) has an arm with which it can perform contact inspection of the surface of a tank. The full state machine in Figure 23 is relevant for the AEROX. Since several of its operations are controlled by the pilot as described in Section 2.5, the operation of the state machine and its transitions is not autonomous but controlled directly by the pilot. The Localization block uses the method described in Section 2.5.3.

3.7 Validation

The presented control structure has been tested with a software in the loop simulation of the VIAD-DRONE aerial robot, which implements the full controller structure shown in Figure 22.

The mission is the target installation, which aims to fix a target label at a predefined point in the pillar of a viaduct for accurate measuring of defects with a high resolution camera, as described in Section 2.6.2.

Figure 31. Target placement in viaduct pillar by the VIAD-DRONE.

The mission is sketched in Figure 31. First an approach trajectory is defined normal to the pillar surface at the target placement point. Then, the robot is guided to follow the trajectory until it touches the pillar surface. Once it has contacted the pillar, the contact is maintained for one second and then the aerial robot is commanded to separate from the pillar and go back to the base. Figure 32 and Figure 33 show the evolution of the position coordinates during the approach, contact and separation phases.

Figure 32. Position of the VIAD-DRONE in the target installation.

Figure 33. Velocity of the VIAD-DRONE in the target installation.

The contact observer is used to precisely detect the time instant the aerial robot end effector touches the pillar surface and modify the commanded velocity of the robot. Figure 34 shows the evolution of the contact index used to detect the contact.

Figure 34. Contact detection in target installation.

4. Conclusions

With respect to the localization algorithms, the deliverable presents different methods taking into consideration the specificities of each use case. In the case of AERO-CAM, the proposed algorithms allow the performance of general and specific visual inspection missions on viaducts within the PILOTING project. The choice of sensors has proved to be the right one, achieving sufficient accuracies for this type of inspections. In addition, this update of the algorithms has shown a remarkable progress in performance since the previous iteration, consolidating the development. All this has been validated in a totally real scenario with high repeatability, performing the whole operation in a autonomous way.

On the other hand, the method shown for the AEROX allows performing contact inspections in tanks with high accuracy. Although this methodology requires a total station and the partial intervention of the pilot in the first phase of the flight, the aerial platform is able to fly autonomously with high precision while the contact phase is being performed, allowing the measurements to be carried out in a totally accurate way and referenced to the previous 3D model. In relation with HYBRID, a method has been presented that allows the navigation and location of pipelines to land on them and perform contact inspections. Although this method has been validated with realistic experiments on a mockup, its validation on the aerial platform is pending once the aerial platform is ready to fly.

The proposed VIAD-DRONE GNSS-free localization method allows to autonomously complete the set of missions envisioned for the PILOTING viaduct scenario (*target installation, bearing inspection, and sensor installation*). These missions require physical contact with the viaduct deck and pillar, which impose strong accuracy and robustness requirements on the pose estimation system. The proposed VIAD-DRONE localization method makes use of extensive multi-sensor fusion that releases the need of using large and heavy sensors (using several lightweight sensors instead), reduces the computational cost involved, and naturally increases robustness due to its multi-sensor nature. The localization system has been extensively validated with high repeatability while the robot autonomously performs the actual missions in the real scenarios. The evaluation of the results shows the accuracy and robustness of the method.

On the other hand, the proposed TTDRONE GNSS-free localization method allows to autonomously complete the PILOTING tunnel inspection mission. It makes use of extensive multi-sensor fusion that releases the need of using large and heavy sensors (using a number of lightweight sensors instead), reduces the computational cost involved, and naturally increases robustness due to its multi-sensor nature. The localization system has been validated with high repeatability while the robot autonomously performs the actual missions in the real scenarios. The evaluation of the results shows the accuracy, robustness, and repeatability of the developed method.

Finally, the general aerial control structure presented in the document allows PILOTING aerial robots safe and reliable flight during their operations in the different use cases. A state machine that covers the flight phases in free flight, approach and contact operations is defined and adapted for implementation in the different aerial robots. Contact and force observers are used to detect contact

with the surfaces, which induce structural changes in the dynamics and control, and are managed by the Control Manager. The contact and force observers have been validated with experiments in a viaduct. The control scheme also includes a trajectory follower for the approach flights and the attitude and position controllers. The control structure has been tested with a software in the loop simulation of the VIAD-DRONE aerial robot, which implements the full controller structure and state machine, in the target installation mission.

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